

MODELING & FINITE ELEMENT ANALYSIS (FEA) OF ATV CHASSIS TO ENHANCE EFFICIENCY

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Abstract:

The automotive chassis provides the strength necessary to support the vehicular components and the payload placed upon it. The suspension system contains the springs, the shock absorbers, and other components that allow the vehicle to pass over uneven terrain without an excessive amount of shock reaching the passengers or the cargo. The steering mechanism is an integral portion of the chassis, as it provides the operator with a means of controlling the direction of travel. The tyres grip the road surface to provide good traction that enables the vehicle to accelerate, brake, and make turns without skidding. Working in conjunction with the suspension, the tyres absorb most of the shocks caused by road irregularities. The body of the vehicle encloses the mechanical components and passenger compartment. It is made of relatively light sheet metal or composite plastics. The components which make up the chassis are held together in proper relation to each other by the frame. Through this research paper, our endeavour is to develop and design a Chassis for ATV and to conduct its Finite Element Analysis using various software required for the same in order to develop robust and efficient ATV chassis design.

Keywords : Automobile, Component, Mechanism, Steering, Vehicle, Etc.

1) Introduction

Finite Element Analysis (FEA) remains computer aided method of simulating/analyzing the behavior of engineering structures and components under a variety of situations. It is a modern engineering tool that is used in design and to augment/replace experimental testing and analyzing the chassis of vehicles before fabrication of the same.

FEA is compulsorily accepted in almost all engineering fields. The methodology usually used as an alternative to the experimental test method set out in numerous standards. The technique is based on the premise that an average solution to any automobile based engineering problem can be reached by subdividing the structure or component into smaller more manageable (finite) elements. The Finite Element Modeling is analyzed with a greater precision than would otherwise be possibly using conventional hand based analyses, since the adequate shape, load and constraints, as well as material based property combinations can specified with much greater accuracy than other used in classical hand calculations.

(I) Pre-processing:

In Pre processing, the analyst develops a finite element mesh of the geometry and applies material based properties, boundary conditions and loads applicable for the same.

(II) Solution:

During solutions, the program derives the governing matrix equations -

$$(\text{stiffness} \times \text{displacement} = \text{load})$$

From the FEA model and solves for the displacement based, strains and stresses based analysis. This is the case in with the implicit code applications. Alternatively explicit coding can be used in numerous ways, mostly for high strain rate engineering problems.

(III) Post-processing:

In post processing, which the analyst obtains results usually in the form of deformed shapes, contour plots etc. which help to check the overall validity of the solution available. A variety of reporting tools can be used to illustrate the complete behavior of the progressive analysis model inclusive of color contour with vector plots, section cuts/iso-surfaces/animations/graphs and text output. The obtained results are interpreted and areas of concerns are discussed along with the observations.

Fig: FEA Analysis Work Chart

FEA analysis is particularly applicable for:

- I. Structural/mechanical engineering design
- II. Product development
- III. Manufacturing processes
- IV. Improving the efficiency of existing designs
- V. Failure analysis investigations.

In this research paper, to fulfill our endeavour such as to Understand the FEA analysis and its impact on Frame and Chassis design, Design and development of ATV chassis using SOLIDWORKS/CATIA, ANSYS of developed ATV chassis, FEA analysis of proposed chassis, Feasibility study and observations we have worked in systematic manner and the work is described in this paper ahead.

2) Review of Literature:

Many of the early attempted research works in the field of FEA based chassis design and analysis were limited to the computational stress distributions and fatigue life in the chassis with many assumptions taken during computational analysis.

Miner in 1945 explained the fatigue damage during the initiation of crack phase. Damage happens during the initiation phases can be related to dislocations, acquired slip bands, determined micro cracks, etc.

Another researcher, Gurney (1976) propounded that the analyses carried out in this work were restricted to final results which had been obtained for K-butt joints under axial loading and transverse non load carrying fillets which are welded under both axial and bending loading situations.

Tanaka et al (1981) has researched about the stress analysis of a conventional truck chassis which has riveted joints. It was performed by using FEM tool.

Wolfgang Fricke (2002) reviewed the literature on fatigue based analysis of welded joints, which concentrates mainly in papers and books published during the past 10–15 years for the same issue.

Mr. Deprez et al (2005) discussed about off-road vehicles and demonstrated that a lot of effort still has to be included into the design of efficient seat and cabin related suspensions.

Izzudin B. Zaman (2006) conducted a case study on its applications of different dynamic correlation and other model updating techniques. These techniques were used sometimes to develop better refinement models of existing conventional truck chassis with approximately 1 ton and also for overall verification of the analyzed FEA models of conventional truck chassis

Prawoto et al (2007) had discussion of some automotive suspension coil spring, their other fundamental stress distributions, adequate materials characteristic, Product manufacturing and other common failures.

Miyake et al (2008) in his studies requires influencing variables and causes of hot forging die method failures for automotive components are summarized below.

Daowu Zhou et al (2010) quotes about the fatigue module present in (OPTWELD) and takes into accounts of welding residual stresses and distortion in the structures.

Haval Kamal Asker et al (2012) initiated its research in the field of frame of the standard dump truck which supports all types of complicated load arriving from the road and freight being loaded in it.

3) **FEA of ATV**

An Automotive chassis is most important part of any automobile industry weather it is automobile manufacturing or service or selling related industry. The vehicle chassis serves as a framework in order to supporting the body and other different parts of the automobile system. Also, it must be rigid enough to withstand the different amount of shock, generated twist, vibration and other stresses elements. Apart from stress, overall strength remains an important consideration in chassis design so that chassis can have adequate bending stiffness for better handling characteristics. That is why we can say that strength and stiffness are two important critical factors for the design of the chassis all-together. This research work is the work performed towards a static structural analysis performed for a All-Terrain Vehicle chassis.

Fig: ATV Chassis design using Solidworks.

The Structural systems like the Vehicle chassis can be easily analyzed using the finite element techniques studied so far. So, a proper finite element based model of the chassis is to be developed in this thesis. The chassis is modeled in Solid Works (Latest Version). FEA is done on the modeled chassis which used the Solid Works Simulation and ANSYS.

To begin with the initial design of the frame, some design guidelines were essentially required to be set which included intended transmission of the vehicle, steering and suspension system assembly and their placement/installation, mounting of occupant's seat, design features and manufacturing methodology.

III. DESIGN & CALCULATION OF ROLL CAGE

➤ This **Basic specifications of the roll cage**

- (I) Total length of the roll cage : 2200mm
- (II) Maximum height of the roll cage: 1556.52mm
- (III) The Wheel Base of the roll cage : 1450mm
- (IV) The Max Width of the roll cage : 760mm
- (V) Gross weight of roll cage : 220.058kg
- (VI) diameter of the pipe : 32.5mm
- (VII) Inner most diameter of the pipe : 15.2mm
- (VIII) Total length of pipe used : 45.992 mtr
- (IX) The material used is AISI 4130.

➤ **Calculation of forces applied:**

The average amount of vertical forces which are acting on the front and rear sides of an ATV roll cage is calculated. Maximum applied vertical force which is acting on one of the wheels at the rear is -

$$= 4.50 \times R \dots\dots\dots (1)$$

$$= 4.5 \times 117.62500 = 533.81250 \text{ kgs}$$

Maximum applied vertical force which is acting on the one side of the rear most portion of the roll cage,

$$= P \sin \theta = 533.812500 \sin \theta \dots\dots\dots(2)$$

$$(54.215100) = 6850.383200 \text{ Newton}$$

Maximum overall vertical force acting on another one of the wheels at the front

$$= 4.50 \times R = 4.50 \times 63.87500$$

$$= 287.437500 \text{ kgs.}$$

Maximum overall vertical force acting on one side of front portion of the roll cage system

$$= P \sin \theta = 287.437500 \sin \theta \dots\dots\dots (3)$$

$$(61.449800) = 3272.360700 \text{ N}$$

IV. FEA CALLCULATIONS

Using the applied projected vehicle/driver mass of minimum 400.00 kgs, the impact of force was calculated base on an applied G-load of

$$4.0 F = m.a. \dots\dots\dots (1)$$

$$= 400 \times 4 \times 10.00 = 16000.00 \text{ Newton}$$

$$\text{Impulse time} = \text{weight} \times (\text{velocity per load}) \dots\dots\dots (2)$$

$$= 400.00 \times (16.67.00/16000.00) = 0.320 \text{ seconds}$$

We apply 16000.00 Newton from the front side for the test of front Load impact of the roll cage structures of the applied vehicle for determining the overall strength at the time of front collision.

Fig: Load Calculations system

Maximum Von/Mises Stress = 149.28 MPa

Some Incorporated Factor of Safety= $(\sigma)_{yt}/(\sigma)_{max} \dots (3)$

$$= 355.00/149.280 = 2.380$$

As a factor related to Safety for automobiles goes up to 8.00, hence the applied design is safer against specified stress.

Using the projected vehicle/driver model with applied mass of 400.00 kg, the overall impact force was to be calculated base on a G-load of 4.00 .

$$F = ma = 400.00 \times 4.00 \times 10.00 = 16000.00 \text{ Newton}$$

Impulse time = weight $\times$ (lead velocity/applied load)

$$= 400 \times (16.670/16000.00) = 0.320 \text{ seconds timing}$$

We have applied 16000.00 Newton load from the very front for the test of rear impact of the roller cage structure of the proposed vehicle for determining strength at the time of rear collision.

Fig: rear force calculation.

Maximum Von Mises Stress= 186.86 MPa

Lead Incorporated Factors of vehicle Safety

$$= (\sigma)_{yt}/(\sigma)_{\text{maximum}} = 365.00/186.86 = 1.9536$$

As a leading factor of Safety for designed ATV goes up to 8, hence the design is safe against specified stress applied to the cage.

Using the approximate projected vehicle/driver mass of approximately 400.00 kg, the impact force was calculated base on a G-load of other area.

$$F = ma$$

$$= 400 \times 2.0 \times 10.00 = 8000.00 \text{ Newton}$$

It is known that –

$$\text{Impulse time} = \text{weight} \times (\text{velocity/load})$$

$$= 400.00 \times (16.670/8000.00) = 0.16 \text{ seconds approx}$$

We apply minimum 8000.00 Newton from the both of the side for the test to determine the side impact of the designed ATV roll cage structure of the vehicle for calculating the strength at the time of side collision of ATV.

Maximum deformation:

16.834 mm calculated Maximum deformation for the side based impact is also under the safe limit & not affects the overall safety of driver,

$$\text{In order to calculate the maximum Von-Mises Stress} = 194.71 \text{ MPa}$$

$$\text{Incorporated the described Factor of Safety} = (\sigma)_{yt}/(\sigma)_{\text{max}} = 355.00/194.71 = 1.823$$

As a determining factor of Safety for automobiles goes up to 8, hence design is much more safer against specified stress analysis.

5) Strain and Stress Analysis

This Stress and Strain Analysis of all the parts of ATV was done using Autodesk inventor. The front lower wishbone was get tested as the strut is attached on its lower wishbone due to which the most of the load are acted on the lower wishbone. The ATV wishbone was then tested in Autodesk inventor. The two basic hinge points and the ball joint are considered as the fixed points and a load of 2586.59 Newton (load on springs) was then applied at the strut attachment point.

Fig: Stress analysis of front mounting.

6) Observations and Results:

After completing the design of Roll Cage of ATV, its frame along with its material and cross section, the essential next step remains to test the rigidity and strength of the frame under severe conditions which is being done in ANSYS. As per the FEA Analysis it is to be find that the frame is able to withstand the impact, torsion, roll over conditions and provide utmost safety to the driver without undergoing much deformation.

Following tests were performed on the roll cage under the proposed FEA analysis:

1) Frontal impact test of Roll Cage

2) Wheel bump Dimension test

3) Longitudinal Torsion test for roll cage impact assessment

It is seen from the figure described above, the maximum stress value in the roll cage equals 1027.75KN/Sq. inch (1591.3 MPa) which seems to be exceeded to the safe value of 267.00KN/Sq. Inch. Hence modifications are needed to be made in the design. The Bracing members needed to be added in the chassis. Also some other members are added to the final roll cage frame to channelize the stress throughout the finite members of the roll cage design. Also the adequate positioning of its engines, gearbox component and suspension needs to be modified which is resulting in the applied changes to the roll cage system.

Results:

After the finalization of the desired ATV frame with the material and cross section of it, it is very essential to test the ATV's rigidity and the final strength of the frame under severe degradable conditions. As far as the design is concerned, the proposed roll cage is designed with a mere two box assembly which consist of the driver's cabin and the engine cabin. The steering system and its drum brake system which is integrated to the driver's cabin.

The ATV roll cage is designed so as to carry a driver of approximately 120kgs along with a fire extinguisher of 2kgs an engine of approximately 23kgs and a fine tuned gear box with differential arrangement of 16.5kgs. The beams which used are pipes with appropriate thickness. Pipe of circular some cross section which used, is get selected due to its availability in the local market and its relatively ability to withstand various forces.

Under the FEA analysis, there are following tests were performed on the designed roll cage

- (i) Front impact test
- (ii) Side impact test
- (iii) Rear impact test

Impact load calculation:

In FEA analysis,

With using the projected ATV vehicle without the driver mass of 455 kg,

The impact force was calculated based on a G-load of

$$4. F = ma =$$

$$455 \times 4 \times 10 = 18200 \text{ N}$$

The Impulse time = weight $\times$ (velocity/load)

$$= 455 \times (16.67/18200) = 0.416 \text{ seconds}$$

We apply 18200 N from the front side for the test of the rear impact of the ATV roll cage structure of the proposed vehicle for finally determining the strength at the time of rear collision system.

Maximum deformation:

17.5010 mm Maximum deformation taken place for the rear impact done by simulation and it is also under the safe limit & not firmly get affects the safety of driver's cabin.

Maximum Von Mises Stress counted = 156.860 MPa

The Incorporated Factor of Safety = $\sigma_{yt} / \sigma_{max}$

$$= 355.00/156.860$$

$$= 2.260$$

As with the results of this FEA analysis, the factor of Safety for automobiles goes up to 8 points, hence the design is pretty good safer against the specified stress previously tested.

The Side impact analysis

The Impact load calculation is performed using the projected ATV vehicle/driver mass of 455 kgs,

the impact force was calculated on the basis of a G-load of approximately 2.

Then

$$F = ma = 455 \times 2 \times 10 = 9100 \text{ N}$$

The Impulse time = total weight $\times$ (velocity of vehicle / pay load)

$$= 455 \times (16.67/9100) = 0.8335 \text{ seconds}$$

We had applied upto 9100 Newton force from the side for the test of side impact of the designed ATV roll cage structure of the vehicle for determining strength at the time of the particular side collision.

And after the FEA and roll ccage simulation and calculation based result analysis we find that the Maximum VonMises Stress = 184.710 MPa

With Incorporated Factor of Safety = σ_y / σ_{max}

$$= 355.0/184.710 = 1.920$$

As the final factor of Safety for ATV based automobiles goes up to 8points, hence design is considered safe and secure against specified stress and the designed roll cage is also selected for the fabrication.

7) **Conclusion**

The FEA analysis of an ATV, in this study, demonstrated the structural superiority of the proposed roll cage design while maintaining a lower weight to strength ratio in proper manner. The customers' utmost needs were remain taken the top most priority because they are remain the ultimate goal of every automobile manufacturer.

The ATV vehicle design, in this FEA analysis demonstrated the desired satisfactory dynamic stability while maneuvering rough terrains in simulation. The proposed design of the ATV vehicle is kept very simple keeping in view its manufacturability and other desired specifications. Thus at this point of time our ATV design can be barely redacted to heading in correct direction. There is a lot of future work which is much essentially required to fine tune the overall performance of ATV in real situations. The design analysis, its development and fabrication now can be carried out based on the FEA results with great success. The designed roll

cage is than used to build an ATV by integrating most of all other automotive systems like the transmission, adequate suspension, adequate type of steering, hydraulic brakes and the other miscellaneous elements.

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